

Excited State and Product Wavefunctions for the One Dimensional Dirac Equation

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In a previous note, the nonrelativistic bound state wavefunction $W(x)$ was written as $W_0(x)W_1(x)$ with $W_0(x)$ being the ground state wavefunction. $W_1(x)$ satisfies an eigenvalue equation, similar to the Schrodinger equation, but with the potential term replaced with a coupling term:

$$-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W_1(x) - 1/m \frac{d}{dx} W_1(x) \left[\frac{d}{dx} \frac{W_0(x)}{W_0(x)} \right] = (E-E_0) W_1(x) \quad ((1))$$

Mathematically, ((1)) may be compared to the hypergeometric differential equation and solutions found for the Schrodinger if coefficients meet certain criteria. A similar approach applies to the Klein Gordon and Dirac equations. In this note, we wish to examine possible physical significance of $W_0(x)W_1(x)$. In addition, we wish to obtain an equation, analogous to ((1)) for both the Klein Gordon and Dirac equations to compare the coupling terms.

Physical Aspects of $W_0(x)W_1(x)$?

One may mathematically write $W(x)=W_0(x)W_1(x)$ where $W(x)$ is a bound state wavefunction of either the Schrodinger or Klein Gordon equation and $W_0(x)$ a ground state solution. For the Dirac equations in one dimension, one may use: $v(x)=v_0(x)v_1(x)$ and $u(x)=u_0(x)u_1(x)$. This leads to a coupled equation for $W_1(x)$ (with $W_0(x)$) with the potential $V(x)$ absent. This equation is of the form of a second order differential equation. It may be compared to a hypergeometric differential equations and solutions for $W_1(x)$ or ($v_1(x)$, $u_1(x)$) obtained if certain criteria are met (1).

A question arises as to whether there is physical significance to such an approach i.e. is there any physical presence of $W_0(x)$ and $W_1(x)$ in $W(x)$. One may argue $W(x)$ is the solution of an excited state, with Fourier series terms $\exp(ikx)$ being related to plane waves with momentum k . With $W_0(x)$ and $W_1(x)$, there are two Fourier series, but only one particle. If one writes the nonrelativistic flux, one has:

$$\frac{d}{dx} W(x) / W(x) = \frac{d}{dx} W_0(x) / W_0(x) + \frac{d}{dx} W_1(x) / W_1(x) \quad ((2))$$

It is as if there are two resonances present at the same time. A particle may belong to the $W_0(x)$ resonance at one moment, and to the $W_1(x)$ resonance at another. This may seem unusual at first, but even with the Fourier expansion of $W(x)$, a particle may be in a plane wave state with momentum k_1 at one instant and in another plane wave state k_2 at another. One may ask whether any experimental backing exists for such a suggestion. In this note, we argue a "resonance particle" such as a photon or phonon may be emitted when a system moves from $W(x)$ to $W_0(x)$. If the $W(x)$ is a hybrid of two resonances, $W_0(x)$ and $W_1(x)$, it seems it is already

“prepared” for emitting a resonance particle (photon or phonon). A similar argument exists for absorption. In other words, we argue that the frequency of the resonance particle is important and note that for the nonrelativistic and Klein Gordon cases, the coupled equation for $W_1(x)$ also has an eigenvalue related to extra energy above E_1 , i.e. the energy of the emitted photon or phonon.

One may note from ((1)) that this coupled equation has an “interaction” term related to $d/dx W_0 / W_0$ and $d/dx W_1 / W_1$, i.e. the nonrelativistic spatial fluxes. One may also note, however, that $d/dx d/dx W / W$ may also be written in terms of such flux:

$$d/dx [d/dx W_0 / W_0] = (d/dx d/dx W_0) / W_0 - (d/dx W_0 / W_0) (d/dx W_0 / W_0) \quad ((3))$$

Lack of Action-Reaction?

One puzzling point is the presence of $W_0(x)$ and $W_1(x)$ in the coupled equation ((1)), while the Schrodinger or Klein-Gordon equation for $W_0(x)$ contain only $W_0(x)$ and the potential. $V(x)$ Thus, the coupling term in ((1)) $d/dx W_0 / W_0 d/dx W_1 / W_1$ does not seem to create a “reaction” term in the Schrodinger or Klein-Gordon equation. As a result, perhaps this coupling should not be viewed as a force reaction. In other words, the term $V(x)W_0(x)$ in the Schrodinger equation may be rewritten with $V(x)$ and $W_0(x)$ expressed as Fourier series. Then:

$$V(x)W_0(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ (Sum over } k+j=p \text{ } V_k \text{ } f_{0j}) \text{ exp}(ipx) \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{Where } W_0(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } f_{0k} \text{ exp}(ipx)$$

In other words, a given f_{0p} seems to be created from other f_{0j} combining with the potential. The term $d/dx W_0 / W_0 d/dx W_1 / W_1$ does not seem to be of the same nature perhaps. Furthermore, there is only one particle, so it is either part of the W_0 or the W_1 resonance, although it seems to switch back and forth in time, if W_0 and W_1 have physical meaning.

Klein-Gordon Equation with a Scalar Potential

The Klein-Gordon Equation separates in terms of $W(x)=W_0(x)W_1(x)$ in a very similar manner to the Schrodinger case ((1)) i.e.:

$$-d/dx d/dx W_1(x) / W_1 - 2 [d/dx W_1(x) / W_1(x)] [d/dx W_0(x) / W_0(x)] = E^*E - E_0^*E_0 \quad ((5))$$

Dirac Equations with a Scalar Potential

The Dirac equations with a scalar potential may be written as:

$$-d/dx v(x) = (E - m_0 - V(x)) u(x) \quad ((6a))$$

$$d/dx u = (E + m_0 + V) v(x) \quad ((6b))$$

In the nonrelativistic limit, $u(x)$ satisfies the Schrodinger equation (time independent) and $v(x) = 1/2m d/dx u(x)$.

In general ((6a)) and ((6b)) yield:

$$[-d/dx v / v] [d/dx u / u] = (E + m_0 + V(x)) (E - m_0 - V(x)) \quad ((7))$$

Thus, if one writes $v(x) = v_0(x)v_1(x)$ and $u(x) = u_0(x)u_1(x)$ then:

$$[-d/dx v_0/v_0][d/dx u_0/u_0] = (E_0 + m_0 + V)(E_0 - m_0 - V) \quad ((8)) \text{ and}$$

$$[d/dx v_1/v_1][d/dx u_1/u_1] + [d/dx v_0/v_0][d/dx u_1/u_1] + [d/dx v_1/v_1][d/dx u_0/u_0] = (E)^*(E - E_0) \quad ((9))$$

In the nonrelativistic limit, $v_0 = 1/2m d/dx u_0$, $E_0 + m_0 + V = 2m$ and $E_0 - m_0 - V = E_0 - V$, so ((8)) becomes the time-independent Schrodinger equation and ((9)) becomes:

$$[d/dx v_1/v_1][d/dx u_1/u_1] + [d/dx d/dx u_0/d/dx u_0][d/dx u_1/u_1] + [d/dx v_1/v_1][d/dx u_0/u_0] = (E)^*(E - E_0) \quad ((10))$$

and

$$v_1 = (d/dx u) / [(E - E_0)v_0 + d/dx u_0] \quad ((11))$$

In the nonrelativistic limit: $v_1 = (d/dx u) / (d/dx u_0)$

Thus, ((10)) becomes a second order nonrelativistic DE in $u_1(x)$ i.e.

$$\{d/dx u_1/u_1 + d/dx u_0/u_0\}(1/v_1) u_0 / (d/dx u_0) d/dx d/dx u_1 + \{d/dx u_1/u_1 + d/dx u_0/u_0\} (1/v_1) d/dx u_1 \{2 - u_0 d/dx d/dx u_0 / (d/dx u_0 d/dx u_0)\} + [d/dx d/dx u_0 / d/dx u_0][d/dx u_1/u_1] = (E)^*(E - E_0) \quad ((12))$$

This is a DE in the nonrelativistic limit in the form of:

$$d/dx d/dx u_1 + Q(x) d/dx u_1 + (d/dx u_0) (d/dx u_1 / u_0) F(x) = E^*(E - E_0)u_1$$

where $F(x) = \{2 - u_0 \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} u_0 / (\frac{d}{dx} u_0 \frac{d}{dx} u_0)\}$ and $Q(x) = [\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} u_0 / \frac{d}{dx} u_0]$ ((13))

This reduces to:

$\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} u_1 + 2 (\frac{d}{dx} u_0 / u_0) \frac{d}{dx} u_1 = E^*(E-E_0)u_1$ in the nonrelativistic case, which matches the result from the Schrodinger equation ((1)).

An alternative calculation is given in Appendix A.

In the nonrelativistic limit, u_0 is the solution of the Schrodinger equation, and the coupling equation matches that of the Schrodinger case for $W(x) = W_0(x)W_1(x)$. This is expected as $u(x)$ should become $W(x)$ and $u_0(x)$, $W_0(x)$. Thus, one expects $u_1(x)$ should become $W_1(x)$.

Relativistic Dirac Equation in u_1

One may obtain a second order relativistic DE in u_1 from the Dirac equations.

$\frac{d}{dx} u - v_1 \frac{d}{dx} u_0 = (E-E_0) u_0 v_1$ or

$v_1 = (\frac{d}{dx} u) / [(E-E_0)u_0 + \frac{d}{dx} u_0]$ where $\frac{d}{dx} u = u_0 \frac{d}{dx} u_1 + u_1 \frac{d}{dx} u_0$ ((14))

This yields an equation for v_1 in terms of $\frac{d}{dx} u_1$ and u_1 . If ((14)) is inserted into:

$-\frac{d}{dx} v - u_1 \frac{d}{dx} v_0 = (E-E_0) u_0 u_1$ ((15)) one obtains a second order DE for u_1 .

For example, the coefficient of $\frac{d}{dx} u_1$ is:

$-u_0 \frac{d}{dx} v_0 / \{ B \frac{d}{dx} u_0 \} - v_0 \{ 2/B \} + v_0^* v_0^* u_0^* (1/B) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} u_0 / (\frac{d}{dx} u_0 \frac{d}{dx} u_0)$

where $B = [(E-E_0)/2m + 1]$ This leads to: $-v_0 2/B = -\frac{d}{dx} u_0 (1/m) (1/B)$ where B goes to 1 in the nonrelativistic limit.

This yields the same results as the example given directly above. Thus, there is a second order DE for u_1 which yields the coupled $W_1(x)$ DE from the Schrodinger case in the nonrelativistic limit.

The objective of listing this equation is to see the coupling of $\frac{d}{dx} u_1$ in the relativistic case, namely:

$(\frac{d}{dx} u_1) \{ -u_0 \frac{d}{dx} v_0 (1/F) - v_0 [(\frac{d}{dx} u_0) (1/F) - u_0 (\frac{d}{dx} F) (1/F^2) + \frac{d}{dx} u_0 / F] \}$

where $F(x) = [(E-E_0)u_0 + \frac{d}{dx} u_0]$

In the nonrelativistic limit, the first and the third terms cancel and the second and fourth both become $d/dx u_0$, but in general the relative couplings for the Dirac case are more complicated than for the Klein-Gordon case which mimics the Schrodinger case. Note: In the nonrelativistic case, the flux $d/dx u_0$ couples with $d/dx u_1$, but in the relativistic case, $d/dx v_0$ which is $d/dx \{ (d/dx u_0) / [E+m_0+V(x)] \}$ enters into the picture. It is related to the average of the momentum squared (kinetic energy in the nonrelativistic case) and $d/dx V(x)$. The factor $F(x)$ is related to $d/dx u_0$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue that using $W(x)=W_0(x)W_1(x)$ where $W(x)$ is a full bound state wavefunction and $W_0(x)$ a ground state wavefunction (or some state) leads to two resonance equations which we think have physical meaning. The first is the Schrodinger equation for W_0 and the second, a coupled eigenvalue equation for $W_1(x)$ (which is similar to the Schrodinger equation.) We try to examine a similar form for the one dimensional Dirac case using $u(x)=u_0(x)u_1(x)$ and $v(x) =v_0(x)v_1(x)$ and examine the coupling in both the relativistic situation and nonrelativistic limit.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Scalar Potentials Compatible with a Decoupled Dirac Hypergeometric Equation (preprint, zenodo, 2019)

Appendix A

An alternative nonrelativistic equation leads to the same results presented above.

$$-v_0 d/dx v_1 - v_1 d/dx v_0 = (E-m-V) u_0 u_1 \quad (\text{directly from 6a})$$

and $v_1 = u_1 + [(u_0 / d/dx u_0) d/dx u_1]$ (nonrelativistic) from

$$-v_0 d/dx v_1 - v_1 d/dx v_0 = (E_0-m_0-V) u_0 u_1 \quad \text{from ((6a))}$$

These two lead to a second order DE in u_1 .

The coefficient of u_1 is: $-d/dx v_0 - (E-m-V) u_0$. In the nonrelativistic limit $v_0=1/2m d/dx u_0$ so this factor contains the Schrodinger equation $-d/dx v_0 - (E_0-m-V) u_0 =0$ leaving $-(E-E_0)$.

The coefficient of $d/dx d/dx u_1$ is: $-u_0 v_0 / [d/dx u_0]$ which is $-u_0/2m$ in the nonrelativistic limit.

The coefficient of $d/dx u_1$ is: $-u_0 d/dx v_0 / (d/dx u_0) - v_0 [2 - u_0 d/dx d/dx u_0 / (d/dx u_0 d/dx u_0)]$

In the nonrelativistic limit this yields $-1/m d/dx u_0$ which is the same as the nonrelativistic result.